

Women's Socio-Economic Status in Rural Sector

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Abstract-

The research paper is to examine women's legal understanding about divorce in rural locations. Women are increasingly exposed to domestic abuse and criminal activity in today's society, which has particularly serious divorce difficulties. The cruel deeds that are imposed on women in relation to their marriage or divorce are highlighted. The socio-economic economic situation of rural women, adultery and infidelity, criminal and violent acts against women all have been major considerations in this research.

Keywords:*Divorce, Marriage, Family, Society.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of divorce and separation is not widely known in Indian society. This highlights the very essence of marriage throughout India, which is still severely curtailed by patriarchal socio-cultural conventions and frequently established by members of the family rather than the individuals whom engage into the relationship.

Divorce is still not widely accepted on a social and cultural level, especially when it is undertaken by a woman. In reality, there are many situations where women are urged to stay in an abusive or violent marriage, even by elements of their own natal families. When a divorce or separation does eventuate, men are more likely to be the ones to initiate it.

This is likely due to the fact that women are less likely than men to participate in the workforce, and inheritance practices are still skewed toward men. This limits the option available to women who decide to leave a bad or abusive household. Divorce is a traumatic event Indian society despises. To remove oneself from marital trauma or to voluntarily separate from one's partner, it a very important tool.

A woman needs to be aware of her legal alternatives and rights in order to defend herself from what was supposed to be sacred relationship. Due to a lack knowledge and resources, women are unable to exercise their rights and freedom and cannot obtain the legal representation they

are obliged to. The Indian judiciary structure should be forward-thinking and strive to reduce the disturbing prevalence of marital violence that still exists there.

II. LITERATUREREVIEW

According to Neha, she aimed at giving hope to countless of those women who don't know what to expect while going through the trauma of a marital disaster. The topic which our society uses daily to apply ground-rules and moral policing but it is time we break free from that regressive stigma.

Shashi Deshpande contends that a woman is economically autonomous and makes more money than her spouse. This woman represents modern India because rural Indian women typically receive little attention from their families and earn less than their husbands. They don't have a lot of power over their land. Women are frequently mistreated, subjected to horrible domestic abuse, and faced with challenges relating to gender.

According to Saumya Saxena, she accurately depicts how divorce is frequently mediated by religion. She has been charting the development of Hindu, Christian and Muslim groups in India's marriage and divorce laws. The study demonstrates the distinction between private and public life, individual and collective rights, and the universal law and human rights. The observation is between gender disparity in the late 20th and early 21th centuries and law, religion, family, and minority rights.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. They treated badly, especially by husband.
2. Women's concern over legal discrimination as they don't have much knowledge about laws.
3. They equally have their rights on property.
4. Usually they don't have much opportunities given to them in society.
5. Government should take step to make any law for their improvement in our society.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- To Are women able to raise their voice for divorce in rural areas?
- What issues do women in rural areas have when getting divorced?

III. METHODOLOGY

Secondary sources, including books and articles from different websites, were employed in the examination of women's socio-economic status in rural sector. The issues were divided into components and elements in the study report, and the issues' structure was classified using analytical and descriptive techniques. "The research methodology employed in this work is based on secondary data, which implies it is based on some previously collected information, also known as primary data. In secondary research, the main data is joined and integrated with other data in order to produce what is known as secondary data. Since secondary research is convenient and time-saving, many individuals today opt to go with it.

Divorce first appeared in French vocabulary in the 14th century. During the reign of King Hammurabi of Babylon, the old codified law history of divorce was traced. During that time, a man could divorce his wife simply by saying, "you are not my wife," followed by the payment of a fine and the return of the wife's dowry. However, if the wife wanted a divorce, she had to file a complaint in order to get one. Divorce had begun to gain popularity around the world, and the number of countries seeking to adopt and legalise divorce began to rise. The Vatican City is a state ruled by the head of the Catholic Church, a religion that forbids divorce.

France, where divorce was first legalised in 1762, followed by Germany in 1875, Ireland in 1997, Italy in 1974, and Spain in 1981. France later made divorce illegal in 1816. The history of divorce in the US began in the state of Maryland. South Carolina and Maryland both made divorce lawful in 1701 and 1949 to 1950, respectively. California allowed "no-fault" divorce in 1970. In most nations, divorce needs the approval of a court or other authority in a legal process, which may involve matters of property division, child custody, alimony (spouse support), child support, parenting time, and debt division. Divorce laws vary widely across the globe.

With about 1% of marriages ending in divorce, India has one of the lowest divorce rates in the world. Many couples decide to separate without choosing to file for divorce. Since many marriages are not legally recognised, a divorce in such a partnership would not be included in the statistics on divorce.

In case of Mathura, Hapur and Jhajjar – small town divorce case. According to a member of the bar, many of these lawsuits are brought by women. High court benches make comments about how the increasing number of divorces is "tearing" the social fabric of India. India, with a divorce rate of 1.1%, has one of the lowest rates in the world, but UN research on women found that the number of divorces has doubled over the past 20 years. In India's small towns, including Hapur, Mathura, and Bhopal, the number of women seeking divorce is rising. With increased

career prospects, growing economic clout in tiny rural areas, and a widow into other worlds-where there is a new space and happiness-the trend of independent divorce-seeking women has been on the rise. In family courts, Uttar Pradesh has the highest number of divorce cases pending, according to a 2018 report. According to the Accidental Deaths and Suicides in India 2021 study by the National Crime Records Bureau, between 2016 and 2020, over 37,591 persons committed suicide, of whom 7% were motivated by divorce.

The Hindu Marriage Act is an act of the Indian Parliament enacted as part of the Hindu code bills at the time: the Hindu Succession Act (1956), the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act (1956), and the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act (1956). (1956). Divorce in India is governed by several acts, including the Special Marriage Act (1956), the Dissolution of Marriage Act, and judicial separation (1869).

IV. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The study helps in understanding the issues faced by women in rural areas by getting divorced and how they are suffering from it. The biggest reason for divorce is conflict between the husband and wife, which has negative effects on children. Divorce is not an appropriate thing to do when couples have issues like disagreements, arguments, cruelty, misbehaving with one another or drug abuse. The pressure from society must also be reduced because it is having a bad impact on our generation otherwise, the divorce rate will rise, so this needs to be reduced. Maturity is a crucial element. People will find a mate, but no one believes that we should be mature enough to avoid fighting and inflicting harm to one another. Women in rural areas must take the initiative and stand up for themselves because of the high crime rate and the lack of amenities for women in rural areas people don't allow women to go anywhere.

Under The Hindu Marriage Act, 1955 the basic goal of this law is to safeguard and advance the marriage between a man and a woman. Only after the method outlined in the regulations has been followed to determine the party's reconciliation or dispute resolution may a problematic between two parties be resolved on the basis of the law.

V. REFERENCES

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